

AFINET

AGROFORESTRY INNOVATION NETWORKS

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REPORT ON THE 2ND RAIN WORKSHOP IN PORTUGAL

Summary

This is not needed for the English report.

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

AFINET- Agroforestry Innovation Networks

RAIN- Regional Agroforestry Innovation Networks

KC - Knowledge cloud

PNRN - Portuguese national rural network

IB - Innovation Broker

1. PREPARATORY ACTIVITIES

The preparatory activities included informing all current Portuguese RAIN members about the meeting. For this, two emails were sent:

- one month before the meeting
- second one week prior to date squealed as limit for the registration acting has a final reminder

The meeting was also publically announced on:

- ISA website: <https://www.isa.ulisboa.pt/en/cef/highlights/news/afinet-2nd-rain-meeting>
- Event created in the AFINET public Facebook group: <https://www.facebook.com/events/1591236830958736/>
- Event share and announcement in social media from RAIN members, institutions (CEF, EURAF, UNAC etc.)

Regarding the survey, it was shared with RAIN members in a separate email, requesting for answers. A second email, acting has a final reminder, was also sent 5 days before the survey closure.

Due to the public nature of the meeting it was decided that the first presentation would be: 'Project presentation to the new members'. The second presentation, titled 'Presenting the concepts of the knowledge platform - Knowledge Cloud', focused on explaining the knowledge could (KC) concept in connection to ZENODO and Open Air. An explanation of the KC functionalities was also made to the participants. Finally, feedback and opinions concerning this tools were collected from the participants.

The meeting was followed by a presentation of all participants, including presentation of their expertise, expectations from the project, and relationship to Agroforestry. After the presentations the program was organized in eight thematic sections, corresponding to the main bottlenecks identified by the RAIN during the 1st meeting in 12th September 2017. In order to increase the participation of RAIN members and the discussion among all, each topic was assigned a 'moderator'. The moderator was a RAIN member, with relevant expertise in the subject, and was personally invited by the IB (telephone or email). After the presentation of the topic made by the 'moderator' the flour was open to discussion concerning the theme and possible solutions. Along this process the IB acted also has a moderator and reporter of the main ideas expressed by the participants. The large number of interventions from the RAIN members allowed to conclude in the success of the meeting.

2. AGENDA OF THE 2nd RAIN MEETING

Meeting description	
Brief description	2° Regional Agroforestry Innovation Network (RAIN) meeting
Date	30th of January, 2018
Time	9:00h - 16:30h
Location	Instituto Superior de Agronomia Main Building Room 39

Agenda	
9h00	Welcome and registry of the participants
9h30	Participants presentations
10h00	Project presentation to the new members Joana Paulo (CEF/ISA)
10h30	Presenting the concepts of the knowledge platform – Knowledge Cloud João Palma (CEF/ISA)
11h00	Coffee Break
Ideas and bottlenecks – definition of the right means to disseminate the identified knowledge and ideas	

11h30	<p>Topic 1: New productions; innovations, bottlenecks and market potential Moderator: José Costa Gomes (EDIA)</p> <p>Topic 2: Alternative uses to understory biomass Moderator: Maria Fernandes (CEBAL)</p> <p>Topic 3: Definition of the best agroforestry policies and incentive measures Moderator: Maria do Carmo Bica (RRN)</p> <p>Topic 4: Reducing the time till the start of the production of non-woody products (ex: cork and pine nut) Moderator: Sandra Pires (Hidrosoph)</p>
13h00	Lunch Break (“Salão Nobre” – ISA)
14h30	<p>Topic 5: Protection and promotion of the natural regeneration on silvopastoral systems Moderator: Pedro Silveira (ANSUB)</p> <p>Topic 6: Utilization of tree fodder as animal food: nutritional value and pruning techniques Moderator: Joana Paulo (CEF/ISA)</p> <p>Topic 7: Crop budget and production tables for alternative forestry species Moderator: Paula Soares (CEF/ISA)</p> <p>Other topics and suggestions Moderator: Joana Paulo (CEF/ISA)</p>
16h00	Next steps: from January 2018 to July 2018
16h30	End of the meeting

3. LIST OF ATTENDEES

Table 1 List of attendees of the 2nd Portuguese RAIN meeting

Confidential.

The signed list of attendees was sent separately by email in a pdf file.

4. STAKEHOLDERS TAKING PART ON THE 2nd RAIN MEETING

The majority of stakeholders attending the 2nd Portuguese RAIN meeting (Figure 1 and Figure 2) where practitioners (33,3%), followed by multipliers/advisors (26,7%). The number of policy makers/administration and researchers was the same (20% each).

Number of participants /category (Portugal)

Figure 1. Proportion of each stakeholder category in the 2nd RAIN meeting in Portugal

An effort was made by the IB and the project team to maximize the number of participants in the 2nd RAIN meeting, and therefore increase the project visibility and communication. This was the reason for its public announcement and advertisement in social media such as the public Facebook group ([Agroflorestas PT](#)) that already included, at the time of the meeting, included more than 200 members.

In terms of new stakeholders invite they were:

- CEBAL (<http://www.cebala.pt/index.php/en/>), has leaders of several projects related to *Quercus suber* tree (propagation, cork quality, genetics etc.) and alternative usages of products and sub products from the agriculture, food and forest sectors.
- Pedro Leitão from farm AgroComeal (<https://sites.google.com/view/agrocolmeal>). Responsible by a large farm (600 ha) in the central region of Portugal where traditional agroforestry systems are currently in risk. Possibly an influent farmer in the region.

- Hidrosoph (<http://www.hidrosoph.com/PT/>) experts in irrigation systems and monitoring in several agriculture crops, currently starting several projects with tree species in collaboration to one farmer RAIN member. The possibility to work with ISA on preliminary data and results regarding this innovation in irrigating systems motivate this invitation.
- Prof. Paula Soares from ISA was invited to speak on tools for the estimation of production of 'alternative' tree/shrub species

Figure 2 Participants from the 2nd Portuguese RAIN meeting (30 January 2018, Instituto Superior de Agronomia, Lisbon)

In order to increase the number of practitioners the idea was to organize the meeting outside Lisbon, in the city of Guarda or Almeida (center region of the country). Finally, this was not possible due to the climatic conditions and mobility problems of the participants. The location of the meeting in Lisbon originated the increase of participants included in the category of researchers due to their proximity to ISA. Even so, the posterior interaction and feedback to the rest of the RAIN members, will allow to maintain their engagement and the collection of feedback to the IB.

5. SUMMARY OF THE 2nd RAIN MEETING

The meeting started with a presentation titled: 'Project presentation to the new members'. The second presentation, titled 'Presenting the concepts of the knowledge platform – Knowledge Cloud', focused on knowledge cloud (KC) concept, objectives and functionalities. Feedback and opinions concerning this tool were collected from the participants.

The meeting was followed by a presentation of all participants, including presentation of their expertise, expectations from the project, and relationship to Agroforestry. After the presentations the program was organized in eight thematic sections. A summary of the thematic sections is presented.

Eng. José Costa Gomes (EDIA)

spoke about irrigation, bottlenecks, new emerging productions and market potential in the Alqueva irrigation area (Figure 3). He showed cases of investment failures, and raised agroforestry as one of the possible solutions to reduce risk by diversifying income. Within the Alqueva irrigation perimeter, the speaker identified that the main agricultural productions were olive, almond, corn,

Figure 3 Presentation on the topic 'New productions; innovations, bottlenecks and market potential'

sunflower, rapeseed and poppy. These are promoted by big companies which, in some cases, give technical support and seeds to local land owners, leaving these farmers with little room to make their own decisions. He emphasized that an alternative to these big enterprises may rely in the development of niche products and the investment in products diversification. This is already happening and EDIA has been trying to promote these kind of local innovations, by promoting Technical Conferences, an Aromatics Academy, and by offering advice on some new cultures like pomegranate.

Dr. Custódia Correia (PNRN), alerted to the ongoing negotiations for the new CAP, after 2020. Considering commissioner Phil Hogan's communication, the regulation should change and there will be full aperture to the elaboration of the programs by the member countries. The main objectives will be, as stated in the communication, "those of a viable farm sector delivering food security for our citizens; of sustainable management of our natural resources, climate action, and care for the environment; and of the need to ensure

prosperity for our rural citizens” . The plan will mean achieving goals instead of directly applying measures. The national coordinator assumes that Portugal’ s main target should be climate change mitigation, since these will be brutal for Europe’ s southern countries, and partners were asked to lobby and discuss what the internal program should or should not support and subsidize.

Dr. Maria Fernandes (CEBAL) spoke about alternative uses for understory biomass. Several past and ongoing projects have been addressing this thematic. A given example was the Cistus Rumen - Sustainable use of *Cistus ladanifer*, which focussed on the use of this shrub for bioethanol production, extractives exploitation and essential oils use. This was studied under laboratory conditions, so refers to its productive potential. Unfortunately, its effective use is conditioned by several factors, where the fact that it is still not economically viable to remove and transport Cistus to the productive units (distilleries), which are located in Spain, may be the main one. If local distilleries were to exist, maybe this could turn out to be less expensive, and the added value of the end product could compensate the farmers work of removing their shrubs, which would, in turn, contribute to less fire-prone areas.

Eng. Sandra Pires (Hidrosoft) showed an example from a model and application developed to help its clients predicts water supply needs of plants used in irrigation, and possible ways to adapt it to agroforestry uses. She stressed the need for further collaboration with researchers in order to develop new and better models, focusing on emerging cultures and alternative management options. Please see file: ‘AFINET30012018.pdf’ .

Eng. Pedro Silveira (ANSUB) shared his experience with unbalanced stands, which lack younger stages, and how to use natural regeneration and its advantages over artificial ones in these endangered systems. Some discussion occurred on what alternative management options could be undertaken. Reflorestar Portugal (Reforest Portugal, an informal civil association) representatives mentioned some of the syntropic and permaculture agroforestry methods like “chop and drop” to help improve soil fertility, the keyline method to improve water retention and use of legume trees for further nitrogen fixing. Pedro Silveira also brought up the need for the development of personalized machinery, to help address some of the Montado specific needs.

Prof. Paula Soares (ISA) spoke about the usage of production tables. These include species other than the most commercial ones, like Pyrenean oak (*Quercus pyrenaica*), chestnut (*Castanea sativa*) and walnut (*Juglans regia*). The development of these tables, and of its underlying equations, relies heavily on the long term monitoring of stands.

Throughout the event, there were several **issues** that were **mentioned** repeatedly. They are summarized below:

The fact that there are **problems which have already been identified several decades ago**, leads to questioning whether research has been done in the right direction and whether this research has been correctly disseminated to those who have the power to act (whether politically, or in a practical way).

Regarding the **decline of the Montado**, João Soares, a full-time farmer, has recognized the despondency of seeing the Montado languish, and is extremely committed to working on its recovery, despite seeing that the options are still limited. Pedro Silveira, agreeing with this point-of-view, believes that there's still the need to do much further field investigation, contradicting the projects evaluators notion (being them from national or european levels, from research or investment projects) that innovation necessarily relates to technology.

As for the **recurrent fires**, António Bica, full-time father of two farmers, insisted on the idea of promoting **silvopastoral systems** as a way of reducing the shrub load. He believes that goats are a particularly advantageous solution, since in addition to good "natural brushcutters" they make it possible to take advantage of a series of derived products, such as meat, milk and cheese, which makes the expenses compensated with the gains of sales of these products. He mentioned a project that the University of Aveiro is developing, the virtual shepherd, in which the perimeter of grazing is defined by GPS, and the animal has a GPS collar that will give it a small shock whenever it approaches these limits.

Following the idea of **knowledge transfer**, the most natural and fruitful way seems to be the **face-to-face meetings, at the farm, for discussion of ideas, in a farmer-to-farmer and farmer-to-researcher perspective**.

José Costa Gomes, from EDIA, reinforced this by talking about the success that has been the **'Aromatics Academy meetings'**, between regional aromatics producers and potential interested parties, aimed at disseminating innovative practices. Representatives of the National Rural Network also recognized the value of face-to-face discussions, following the numerous informal meetings and visits they have made to farmers and example farms. João Soares seconded this, since he has been one of the most active participants in his region, within the Rural Network. He recognizes that having close relationships with people who have part of the knowledge, whether researchers or technicians, is an advantage at times when the farmer most needs to discuss the actions to undertake. Representatives of Reflorestar Portugal and the Raiz Permanente have reinforced the need to develop a human culture as well, to include communities in the planning and make use of traditional knowledge around Agroforestry practices.

5.1. Survey Summary Results

Date of launching the survey: 28/12/17

Date of closing the survey: 22/01/18

N° of responses: 15

Table 2 Survey Summary Results of the Portuguese RAIN

Challenges		Average score
PT	Define encouragement mechanism for expanding farm size	4
EU	Improving policy support tools to install and promote agroforestry	5
EU	Reducing legislative uncertainty with regard to tree planting on agricultural land	5
EU	Development of practical guidelines/best management practices for tree and tree understorey management	5
EU	More information on optimal tree/crop/livestock combinations, in order to maximize productivity, soil improvement etc.	6
EU	Informing consumers and society in general about agroforestry and its benefits (both environmental and economic)	5
EU	Access to case studies: showcasing farms which demonstrate good agroforestry practices	5
EU	More information on the costs and benefits of specific agroforestry systems	5
EU	Better understanding of the value chain (supply, demand and marketing opportunities) of agroforestry products (e.g. nuts, fruits, wood products, ...)	5

PT	Finding alternate uses for understorey biomass instead of traditional uses (like livestock beds)	5
PT	Encouragement mechanisms and/or policies for specialized labour	5
PT	Transferring practical guidelines/best management practices knowledge in order to recuperate poor and damaged soils	5
EU	More information on optimal tree/crop/livestock combinations, in order to maximize productivity, soil improvement etc.	6

Written comments to questions in the survey:

Question: Are there any important challenges, needs or bottlenecks missing from the list above? Please describe.

Answers:

- “Integrate good fuel management practices on the areas more likely to have fires.”
- “Grazing: shepherds, social bottlenecks and challenges.”
- “The key to good grazing are good shepherds.”
- “Bringing more people to the country’ s interior lands.”
- “Apiculture should be promoted.”

Question: Select one of the above challenges and describe the best way to address/tackle this challenge according to you.

Answers:

- “Broadly speaking we should promote training and knowledge transfer.”
- “We should have good practical guidelines/best management practices which also support economic growth and be sustainable for farmers. To do so, farmers should be informed about agroforestry, we should promote research on those best management practices, and choose the most well adapted one to each unique case. Farmers need access to training and workshops on model farms and case studies. Consumers should be sensitized on the importance of buying local, to help these systems becoming more and more sustainable.”
- “In order to find alternate uses for understory biomass instead of traditional uses (like livestock beds) we can syndicate/associate people and those groups will transform/use these products, allowing the system to be economically sustainable, and generate employment.”

- “What are good practical guidelines/best management practices? Its essential defining them for each type of agroforestry system, but still keeping in mind there are no “recipes” .”
- “Improving policy support tools to install and promote agroforestry:
- “Policies directed at supporting *Zonas de Intervenção Florestal* (ZIFs), to broaden and expand ZIFs as a support mechanism for agroforestry.”
- “Observe and teach shepherds while they are working”
- “Increase farmer’ s and Multiplier’ s knowledge on the production and supply chain and new marketing opportunities on agroforestry products - new products.”
- “Create gains on agroforestry products using protected designation of origin or similar, to increase demand on these products.”

Question: Select one of the above challenges and describe the best way to address/tackle this challenge according to you.

Answers:

- “Defining incentive mechanisms and policies for specialized labour. The current one is based on empirical experience of long years, so it should be studied in order not to lose this knowledge, but it should also be modernized.”
- “Educate and train farmers and specially multipliers to share and transfer knowledge, including information from companies, legislators, administration, and policy makers; and make sure this knowledge and information reaches the farmers.”
- “Increase knowledge on good practical guidelines/best management practices and profitability for optimal tree/crop/livestock combinations. It’ s crucial to network this know-how and the practical applications. It should be financed, as long as partners keep the information flowing and share experiences and results.”
- “Population on the country’ s interior rural areas should be increased - policies for it.”
- “Alternative agroforestry products should be searched and the best management practices for them should be taught and available for farmers - (e.g. *Opuntia ficus-indica*.)”

Question: Select one of the above challenges and describe the best way to address/tackle this challenge according to you.

Answers:

- “Better understanding of the value chain (supply, demand and marketing opportunities) of agroforestry products (e.g. Nuts, fruits, wood products...) for both farmers and advisors/multipliers. “Monopolies and monopsony of these products do not work, and can potentially worsen problems like robberies and mistrust among

practitioners. The flow of knowledge and shared experiences among practitioners help to achieve better, fairer practices for these productions.”

- “Increase knowledge transfer among farmers and multipliers on the costs and benefits of specific agroforestry systems - the importance of networking for farmers and foresters. “
- “Create policies for socioeconomic incentives to increase population on interior rural areas.”
- “Search for alternate uses for understorey biomass such as part of green manures or fertilizers.”

5.2. Initial List of Innovations/Solutions

- Economical aspects and chain development
 - ✓ Bio economy products: alternative usages for shrub / understory species (ex: bioethanol, essential oils extracts)
 - ✓ On line tools for assessment of production expectations of “ alternative’ ’ tree and shrub species
- Communication and awareness raisin
 - ✓ “ Aromatic plans academy establishment’ ’ promoted at regional/local level by EDIA. Purpose: engage farmers, discuss in the field, join farmers and advisory services in the field, discuss concrete problems, promote dissemination of innovations...
 - ✓ Simulation and communication of ecosystem services provided by agroforestry systems
- Policy and administration
 - ✓ Production of technical and summarizing newsletters including legislation and/or support measures (ex: Portuguese RNN)
- Technical Aspects
 - ✓ Agroforestry in the corners of irrigation pivots
 - ✓ Establishment of adequate technical guideline for cork oak tree selection (considering damage, cork age and climate conditions...) and soil protection after fire events in *Montado* areas.
 - ✓ Tree and pasture irrigation
 - ✓ Translation to Portuguese of the leaflets produced by the Agforward project.

5.3. Knowledge transfer during the 2nd RAIN

Stakeholders frequently referred the inexistence of extensions services and the 'distance' between practitioners and the university/researchers.

Also, the lack of information and knowledge regarding techniques and tree/shrub species guidelines and potentials outside the most common in the country, usually associated to established value chains.

Regarding silvopastoral systems tree regeneration it was referred that one of the main constrains is the lack suitable management operations due to increased costs associated. Two of the most referred ones were: installation of suitable tree protectors (depending on the animal species grazing in the farm) and understory management using alternative techniques to plowing.

5.4. Knowledge cloud feedback

The presentation (Please see file "Powerpoint KC_Jan2018.pdf") showed the concept, the networking capacity and the stable (permalinks concept) and the tool itself. The presentation (Figure 4) focused on how the OpenAire platform works, through several repositories across Portugal and the world, and that, for cases where are no institutions or the institutions don't have a repository, we showed that we created the AFINET repository in ZENODO to allow us to link AFINET with this platform.

Figure 4 Presentation on the title of 'Presenting the concepts of the knowledge platform - Knowledge Cloud'

There was a general positive feedback regarding the concept and most value was added to create permanent links to the material being uploaded to avoid being lost when "projects are finished" .

One aspect referred by one farmer was his lack of time to connect and take the most advantage of these type of tools due to his daily routine at the farm. He also recognized his preference for face-to-face or farms-to-researcher communication since in his experience most of the problems are farm or even plot specific and the technical information available might not be suitable for his conditions.

Another relevant feedback was provided by the coordinator of the Portuguese National Rural Network (PNRN), while recognizing the interest of the platform and the advantage in being connected to Open Air. The PNRN will explore the possibility to add the currently existing resources database (<http://www.rederural.gov.pt/centro-de-recursos>) that it manages to the Open Air, with the support of the AFINET project team from ISA.

Finally, the discussion around publication rights concerning scientific publications and other materials was raised, addressed and clarified.

6. SUMMARY OF CONCLUSIONS OF THE 2ND RAIN

The inclusion of new members in the RAIN and the number of participants in this meeting was considered positive by the project team. Therefore, it is considered adequate the established communication strategy regarding the project team, the IB and the RAIN members.

Although it was not possible to address all of the bottlenecks identified in the meeting of 12th September 2017 in Coruche, in particular the ones presented in a more general perspective (e.g. lack of knowledge transfer), several of the topics addressed were clearly connected during the meeting to concrete actions and materials to produce and disseminate along the next 2 years of the AFINET project.

ANNEX I: signed list of attendees

The signed list of attendees was sent separately by email in a pdf file.